

MUTUAL EFFECT OF CREEP AND MOISTURE SORPTION ON EPOXY MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

5000 hours long tension creep of specimens of epoxy matrix EDT-10 with an equilibrium moisture content up to 5% described with the moisture-time analogy principle. In the creep process of the material absorbing moisture the creep rate increased more than five times and in this mode the levels of deformation were attained which many times surpassed those obtained for specimens with constant moisture content. The tensile stress practically did not change diffusion coefficient, but increased the equilibrium moisture content up to 20% of the value of an unstressed material. Compression effect on the moisture sorption kinetics was not revealed.

Keywords: moisture, sorption, stress, creep, epoxy matrix.

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerous experimental investigations show that the moisture sorbed by polymer composites noticeably changes their mechanical characteristics [e.g.1]. The moisture affects particular the viscoelastic properties of materials which manifest themselves largely in the properties of the matrices. The most of those investigations were made on the specimens with the steady state moisture content. But really the atmospheric humidity, and, therefore, moisture content of the specimens, is not constant during its lifetime. On the other hand moisture sorption processes usually take place in the materials under stress state. So the aim of the present work was to investigate mutual effect of stress and moisture sorption on widespread epoxy matrix EDT-10.

2. CREEP IN A HUMID ATMOSPHERE

2.1 .Experimental details.

The influence of a constant and a variable moisture content on the creep deformation was studied for EDT-10 epoxy matrix, which was prepared from epoxy diene resin and cured with 3-ethanol-aminetitanate. Specimens of 130 mm in length and

with 1x10 mm cross section were preliminary dried in an exsiccator with phosphoric anhydride, and than moistened at a constant moisture of 47, 78 and 98 RH in the exsiccators with saturated solutions of salts. The equilibrium moisture content of the specimens in these conditions was 0; 1,6; 2,7; and 4,8 mass %.

The creep testing in axial tension lasted for 300 days and was performed in chambers of a constant humidity of the atmosphere provided by saturated solutions of salts. A small-size lever device allowed a simultaneous creep tests of four specimens with cross section 0,1 cm² at the stresses of 0..80 MPa. The chamber had a transparent front wall, through which deformation of the specimens was measured by a cathetometer.

2.2.Creep with steady-state moisture content.

Two groups of creep experiments were carried out at a stress up to 20 MPa (about 0,3 of the strength). In the first group of experiments at 20 MPa (fig.1) included only the specimens which had been previously wetted in the exsiccators, and moisture content throughout their cross section was assumed to be uniform. During the creep tests the moisture content of these specimens remained practically unchanged.

The creep deformation of maximally moistened specimens was found to increase in 4..5 times compared with the dry specimens. Analysis of the data of a series of short-time (24 hours) creep testing of moistened specimens showed that residual strain after long time (168 hours) unloading was very small and nonlinearity of creep isochrones at a stress of 20 MPa could be neglected. The deformation, therefore, could be described by a linear model of the hereditary theory of viscoelasticity using the exponential core (fig.1,lines). To describe creep of material with steady-state moisture content, we use the hypothesis of moisture-time analogy [2]. Then full deformation can be represented in the form

$$e'_{11} = e_{11}^0 \left\{ 1 + \sum_{m=1}^M B_m \left[1 - \exp \left(- \frac{t'}{\tau_m} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$t' = t a_w , \quad (2)$$

were $e_{11}^0 = 0,7\%$ - is the nominally instantaneous deformation; a_w - is the coefficient of moisture-time reduction; τ_m and B_m - are the spectrum of the relaxation times and the amplitudes corresponding to them, respectively; t' - is the reduced time. We determined the relaxation spectrum of the material and the coefficient of moisture-time reduction by approximating a series of creep curves (see Fig.1.) by minimizing the object function. The obtained relaxation spectrum of the material is

Table 1.

m	$\ln \tau_m, s$	B_m
1	9.4	0.0101
2	15.4	0.1830
3	19.0	0.6390
4	22.0	1.7600
5	22.4	5.3700

Figure 1. Experimental data on creep of specimens with moisture content 0 (1, \circ); 1,6 (2, Δ); 2,7 (3, \square); 4,8% (4, \circ) and their approximation (1-4).

represented in Table 1. The function of moisture-time reduction is approximated by the empirical dependence

$$\ln a_w = 2.068w - 0.172w^2 \quad (3)$$

Here and henceforth it is understood that the moisture-time reduction is carried out relative to nominally dry material.

The presented results show that creep of moistened binder EDT-10 in the investigated range of steady-state moisture content and at stress of 20 MPa is satisfactorily described on the basis of the linear theory of viscoelasticity with the use of the principle of moisture-time analogy.

2.3. Creep with nonsteady moisture content.

In the second group of experiments the specimens sorbed moisture alongside with the creep. For this purpose initially dry specimens were tested in the chambers of an high humidity. The moisture content of the specimens grew from 0 to 1,6; 2,8 or 4,8% according to the atmospheric humidity of the chamber. Three series of the creep tests were carried out at a stresses of 0, 10, 20 MPa (denoted by the numbers 1, 2, 3, respectively). The relative humidity of the atmosphere of the chambers was 98% (series 1 and 2) and 78% (series 3). The experimental data of creep of the specimens and the change of their moisture content are shown in Fig.2. by dots. The creep curves 2 and 3 (see Fig.2a.) were calculated for the second and third series of experiments by formulas (1), (3) with view to the fact that in this case the reduced time is equal to

$$t' = \int_0^t a_w[w(s)] ds \quad (4)$$

The figure shows that the experimental curves are not described by the model presented above (swelling is taken into account - curves 1 in Fig. 2a, 2b) . The difference between the theoretical and the experimental data, "discrepancy" in deforma-

Figure 2. Experimental and theoretical creep curves (a) of the specimens of series 1(●), 2(◻), 3(◼) with variable moisture content (b).

tion e^d , which depends on the stress and the running moisture content of the specimen, may be approximated by the empirical formula

$$e_{11}^d = (0.13 - 2.0 \cdot 10^{-3} s_{11} + 1.15 \cdot 10^{-3} s_{11}^2) \cdot (w - w_0)^{1.46} \quad (5)$$

(the values of stress s_{11} in MPa, e_{11}^d and w - in %).

Therefore, the creep of specimens of material with nonsteady moisture content can be described by formula

$$e_{11}(s, w, t) = e_{11}^e(s, w, t) + e_{11}^d[s, w(t)] \quad (6)$$

We can resume, that the specimens, which were initially dry and then become moistened simultaneously with the creep, have the creep rate more than 5 times as compared with the uniformly moistened specimens and reached in short time deformation levels, which many times exceeded those of the specimens with a maximal equilibrium moisture content. An empirical dependence has been suggested to describe

behavior, which cannot be explained with the moisture-time analogy. The group of control experiments was approximated [3].

3. MOISTURE SORPTION UNDER UNIAXIAL STRESS

3.1. Experimental details.

The desk stands with chambers, mentioned above in 2.1., were used to realize moisture sorption under uniaxial tension. Compression experiments were made on a thin tubular specimens of 40 mm high, diameter 36 mm and wall thickness 2 mm. Loading was realized in small chambers, which were placed in reversers of testing machines. The constant relative humidity of the atmosphere in the chambers was maintained by saturated salt solutions. Screen action of the grips was taken into account by using of correction coefficient for moisture content determination in tensile tests.

3.2. Experimental results and discussion.

Preliminary analysis of the experimental moisture sorption data (Fig.3) allowed to resume, that the moisture sorption kinetics under tensile stress up to 50 MPa is in good agreement with Fick's law. Therefore equilibrium moisture content of the material and diffusion coefficient were determined by the method described in [4]. The middle value of the coefficient of diffusion at temperature 19-20°C is $D=1,4 \pm 0,3 \times 10^{-6}$ cm²/h, and is almost unchanged under tensile stress in range 0...30 MPa. But the equilibrium moisture content increase up to 20% from its initial value in 98% RH

Figure 3. Initial fragments of moisture sorption curves of EDT-10 under tensile stress effect.

Figure 4. Tensile stress dependence of material equilibrium moisture content. Sign. from fig. 3.

(Fig.4).

The results of sorption experiments indicate that the compression in the stress range up to 40 MPa (this is about 0,5 of the strength) unchanges moisture sorption kinetic. The sorption curves with different stresses were coincided up to the moment of local stability loss of the specimens.

Volume strain measurement results analysis [5] and data obtained early by physical methods [6] evidence that in the material, which moistened under tensile stress, apparently, essentially increases amplitude of vibration of macro molecules and needed for it's provision volume.

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